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Study of Appeals across the Product Categories Used in TV Advertisements: A Content Analysis Approach

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Abstract:

Advertising is an important marketing tool that helps the business world to promote their product and services in the target market. It not only provides information about the products and services available, but also makes people aware about their potential benefits, new launches and also about various schemes offered by companies. Advertisers use various strategies to persuade consumers and appeals are one of them. They try to persuade them either emotionally or rationally providing all required information, helping consumers to take decisions logically. The present study examines the appeals used in television advertisements, and also the types of appeals in different product categories. The method used for the study is content analysis and only television advertisements are analyzed. The result indicates that most of the advertisements have used non humorous appeals- either emotional or rational and only few advertisements have used humorous appeals. The result further reveals that in case of high involvement products, rational appeals are being used whereas of low involvement products humorous and emotional appeals are used.

Key words: Television Advertising, Appeals, humorous, emotional, rational

1. Introduction

Advertisement has become an indispensable tool for the advancement of business, for positioning, promotion & increasing sale of the product. It is a powerful communication force, highly visible & one of the most important tools of marketing communication that helps to sell products, services, ideas, images, etc. It is assumed that advertisement is a form of effective persuasive communication to impart information & knowledge about the product & services and arrests the attention of consumers by arousing interest for acceptance of the product. According to Colley¹ (1964), "Advertising pulls a consumer towards purchasing action through changes in his or her knowledge & attitude responses". He defined advertising "a mass paid communication the ultimate purpose of which is to impart information, develop an attitude and induce action, beneficial to the advertiser generally the sale of the product or services." Thorson and Leavitt² (1992) viewed advertising as the best prophet for purchase. The objectives of advertising are generally to create awareness, knowledge and comprehension of brand & positive degree of conviction or buying intention for the product. It is an efficient source of information for the consumers about the product, quality, new merchandise, new technology & prices.

The television has emerged as most powerful and effective mass media. The growth of T.V and the numbers of T.V channels has been overwhelmingly welcomed by the advertisers. Television has a vast reach in urban and rural areas both and its round the clock transmission facilitates repeated exposure of the advertised products.

It is believed that television is the most authoritative, influential and exciting medium and hence it is considered the most ideal medium of advertising. It has abilities to combine visual images, sound, motion and color. In T.V there is a unique blend of sight, color, movement, sound, timing, repetitions and presentation, which produces quick and good results. These characteristics present the advertisers with maximum opportunity to develop the most creative and imaginative advertising messages than any other medium.

2. What Is Appeal?

According to Kotler³ (1997), advertiser has to put some driving power into the message to make the audience to receive messages. This driving power is called appeal. Every advertising appeal represents an attraction, which arouse consumers' desires. Berkman and Gilson⁴ (1987) defined advertising appeal as an attempt at creativity that inspires consumers' motives for purchase and affects consumers' attitude towards a specific product or service whereas Dahl⁵ defines appeal as message designed to motivate consumer behavior. The statement in the advertisement must be related to the viewers' interests, goals and problems. Belch and belch⁶ (1998) state that advertising appeal is used to attract consumers' attention. Authors have developed different categories for